

The Next Step in Getting the Composite Story Right—Industrialisation of Manufacturing Systems

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THE NEXT STEP IN GETTING THE COMPOSITE STORY RIGHT : INDUSTRIALISATION OF MANUFACTURING SYSTEMS

Advanced composites are here to stay.

This is obvious not only from the fact that I am able to stand up in front of such a large group of interested people at this, the fourth ICCM conference, but also from the detail of the papers describing the considerable work done in material design philosophy and applications engineering. As it has been seen in other papers the new composite designs have come a long way from initial uses of fibre reinforced plastics in the 50's. Designs have now become to move away from metal look-alikes into truly innovative designs using all the best properties of the materials in the optimum manner. This development has opened the door to vastly wider and more efficient uses in mechanical engineering, but the nature of this evolution has been such as to require structures which although often using fundamental design rules are more complex to manufacture.

The results are predictable ; in order to get the quality to the required levels to meet design specifications, manufacturing costs often become unacceptably high. Major efforts are then made to get the manufacturing costs down, but often quality consistency is jeopardized. This would appear to me to now be one of the biggest -if not the biggest hurdle to the successful large scale introduction of composites. I contend that for a huge number of potential composite applications we now have :

- The materials (and the costs are probably becoming about right)
- The design philosophy
- The prototypes,

but we still cannot make products at a competitive price. This paper addresses this last step in achieving practical large scale introduction of composites.

The starting point is reflected if we look at the current uses of these materials where the major applications are still restricted to the aerospace industry. In this industry high manufacturing costs to ensure the high quality are not unusual, and considering the volumes they can be accepted in the short term. However, if we move to the automotive industry where quality and cost must both be optimised, the use of advanced composites has remained at a very low level indeed, often only used as a part proving exercise. Much good work has been done by many companies throughout the world on individual elements of manufacturing technology. I am pleased to be associated with the group in which one of our sister companies, the INGERSOLL MILLING MACHINE CO., has worked with

their customers to develop a range of cost effective machines such as tape-layers, broadgoods processors, routers, etc... However from our observations of facilities currently installed we have found that they generally fall into three main groups :

- 1 - Prototype shops
- 2 - Development of existing glass fibre shops
- 3 - Dream systems.

The first case certainly offers useful manufacturing research and development experience but once production rates climb, chaos ensues with often conflicts in management organisation as well.

The second is perhaps the most common but usually implies an inherent stagnation in the system. When more stringent quality requirements are overlayed onto the existing system, one finds that both the existing and glass production and the new suffer.

In the third case useful M R & D experience can also be gained but normally only with major investment. Commendably, most of these systems try to move well away from traditional knife and spatular approaches but often go so far that to try and implement all the different parts of new technology in one single system means that the poor production manager is always chasing his own tail following ripple effects from trying to solve one single fault in the system. In this case as volumes rise you need an army of people to keep equipment running and actually a bunch of knife and spatular girls to get the production out of the door.

With some very few and commendable exceptions these types of problems can be seen almost anywhere in the engineering industry where people are introducing composite materials. The problem for someone now looking at this industry and deciding whether to move to substitute composites for some more traditional materials is that he finds the justification of a true industrial method is now impossible. To make matters worse the decision makers become impatient with «fads and the buzz words that describe the fads» (1). However, at the same time senior management is being faced with the old dichotomy of two opposing questions : 1) If I invest in advanced production systems today will it be out-of-date in two years time ? or 2) If I do not invest today will I still be able to enter the market in two years time ?

In such a rapidly moving technological situation one can well understand a board of directors being hesitant, and the wait and see route which is often adopted has been regularly shown in the past to generally be disastrous. However, when looking at the introduction of new technologies into the manufacturing process over the last 20 years, it is fair to say that those people, who have taken an aggressive well measured step early on, have usually been seen to be amongst the leaders many years later. Often such companies may well have found that much of their production systems were out-of-date two years after they introduced them (2), but they have had a sufficiently dynamic attitude to realise that the system will constantly evolve and hence much of it may actually need replacing at a much higher rate that we have been used to in the past. What I have said so far tends to give a very black impression, however it is certainly not the purpose of this paper to discourage the introduction of composites but rather to use past experience to ensure that the existing opportunities present themselves are now used in the best way to accelerate the introduction of these materials whilst keeping risks acceptable. In our experience it would appear the careful planning of these manufacturing systems holds key to their long term success.

A good example of how best to introduce (and in some places how not to introduce) new technology can be seen from the early years of numerical control. Sales of these machines went through an initial period of successful sales and then fell off as people became disillusioned by the lack of concrete results. However, in many cases that can be seen from some highly productive systems of today, these early machines could be extremely well used but only when planned into an integrated system which includes all the required support activities and where the upstream and downstream effects of the new technology were well understood then carefully planned for. The same situation I believe exists from the introduction of those manufacturing technologies in composites.

Perhaps the first thing to remember is that, as can be seen from this conference, composite materials cover a multitude of applications. It is important to remember that each production system must respond to a specific need in the industry in question and indeed often to each individual company introducing that technology.

In many of the plants in operation today one can see a desire to be a «Jack of all trades» but we should remember that the whole saying is «Jack of all trades and master of none !» (3) The necessity to focus the activity of the unit is vital in an area of such rapidly moving technology where efforts in

developing the technology should not be diluted across too many conflicting needs.

Having said that I have to remember that I address an audience drawn from many industries and suggestions in this paper as to how to accelerate industrialisation in composites must tend to be rather general and «unfocused».

The second guideline is to have a plan, a long term plan that describes not only how to get started but also where you expect to go and what bench-marks have been set along the way to monitor progress. It seems very obvious, but it is all too easy in the rush of everyday production to fire-fight individual problems, and hence end up growing like topsy in such a rapidly moving technological area, the results can be disastrous.

The initial plan to get started is perhaps not difficult to establish, I will talk a little more of that later, but the plan on how to evolve can require quite a lot of crystal ball guessing. To avoid the trap of falling into the dream systems talked about earlier, it is usually sufficient to describe areas where it can be foreseen what enabling technology will be needed to achieve objectives set in the industrialisation of one of the individual elements of the process. In this way, space can be left or services can be installed to cover this eventuality. An example of this in the aerospace composite area might be in the highly manual lay-up operations.

The third guideline is to integrate. In twenty years as consultants on the business of manufacturing this is perhaps the area where we see the most missed opportunities.

It is surprising how often we see the potential benefits of the excellent work on individual elements of a system being greatly reduced when they all meet up for the first time on the shop floor.

This preoccupation with the individual elements of the system tends to be based in the way all manufacturing men were brought up. Figure 1 shows a typical engineered product cost breakdown of twenty-five years ago.

Figure 1 - Product cost breakdown - early stages of industrialisation

Figure 2 describes the way we tended to attack those costs by dividing responsibility between different groups.

Figure 2 - Division of effort to reduce product costs

However, Figure 3 shows the cost breakdown today for a typical mature industrialised manufacturing system.

Figure 3 - Product cost breakdown - mature industrialisation

The results are obvious in that often the investment required to further reduce direct manpower is excessive and in real terms the financing of that investment may cancel the true cost reduction.

The importance of this situation in the field of composites cannot be overstressed.

The «25 year ago» cost picture (figure 1) equated very closely to that of a «first try» composite shop today. As a result the priorities for cost reduction match those in figure 2 ; but the speed with which results in this area are being achieved means that figure 3 is only just round the corner and we should be planning now to address those problems.

Integration really is the key because getting the material handling right and getting the tool supply well organised, etc..., is what gets the big chunks of cost down.

The last is perhaps the most obvious but perhaps the most difficult guideline, it is quite simply to get started doing something. It is all too easy to say we have to have a plan, we have to know how to integrate, we have to look at the enabling technology... But if all we do is plan, we will not understand what really makes the system tick.

In getting started we are doing much more than just training people or proving a specific piece of product technology. We are understanding those day-to-day nitty-gritty problems which make or break the system. Something can be learned from looking at other people's problems but much, you have to learn on your own. You have to know where the existing factory organisation is just not correctly adapted to handle composites. That which is a major priority problem elsewhere may not even be a problem in your own plant. However there will be other holes in your system which will be fundamental to long term success.

Getting a system started and then executing the plan to evolve over the years requires an enormous flexibility from the managers and planners involved in the shop. It is worth remembering that, with very few exceptions, we are not on the business as philanthropic experimenters. We have got to get the product out of the door and make money. As such, production managers will have to respond to continuous conflicts and almost continuous painful upheavals in their shops. However, although we all crave for stability -it is easier to manage- it is also the easy way to get left behind and become uncompetitive. Having a plan to get started in a logical and well integrated way helps, but choosing the right people who can move with the times to manage the facility as it evolves is just as important.

For the future we can certainly all agree that the introduction of composites will succeed, the design philosophy is there, the materials are becoming available at a sensible price, many of the individual elements of equipment are there. If we take the trouble we can have a plan ; we can plan to evolve whilst maintaining a good integrated production facility, but what ideas might be encouraged whether within our companies or elsewhere to make our jobs easier.

With regard to materials technology I think we must give considerable credit to suppliers for keeping up with the fickleness of their customers between broadgoods, tape, fibres, filaments, all sorts of curing temperature resins, etc... However unquestionably the matrix technology is a subject where there is potential to minimise bottlenecks and complexities in the manufacturing system.

In the aerospace industry autoclave curing cycles are such that, to maintain flexibility, very specific production control problems are evident. The problems are not insoluble but in practical terms it is an area where our friendly production manager will see the cumulative effects of minor problems elsewhere. As an example a radically new approach to the use of matrix materials could bring major gains.

In product design there must be an ever increasing interface with the manufacturing function. When I spoke of integration earlier I probably should have stressed the importance of integrating the engineering function. This is not a situation special to composites and the advances that have been seen in CAD/CAM are impressive. However, composites are a bit special in that the design often implies a unique manufacturing process and none other. With our focused factory, optimisation is all important.

In addressing our conversation to the equipment builders, we must obviously help them to understand the specific local integration needs. They do an excellent job of coming up with creative designs to respond to specific equipment specifications but the understanding of integration needs are essential for success. Equally we should remember the example above of the initial years of numerical control, where initial equipment problems due perhaps to overly ambitious aims, clearly slowed the introduction of the whole technology.

To conclude, composites are here to stay for many reasons. Their mechanical performance is impressive, corrosion resistance is exceptional, etc..., etc... All these advantages are being demonstrated by many people but from some of the work that we and others are doing at the moment, there appears a potential to make a key reason for introducing composites that they are in fact cheaper to manufacture.

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